

Polynomial Contraction in Logarithmic Blocks for the Shortened Collatz Transformation, for a Logarithmic Density 1 of Integers

Romain Peter

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Abstract

We consider the "shortened" Collatz transformation $T : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ defined by $T(n) = n/2$ if n is even and $T(n) = (3n + 1)/2$ if n is odd. Fixing parameters $\tau \in (0, \tau_c)$ with $\tau_c = 1/\log_2 3 - 1/2$, $\lambda \in (0, 1/\ln 2)$, and $\beta \in (0, 1)$, we show that for $L(n) = \lfloor \lambda \ln n \rfloor$ there exists $\gamma > 0$ such that, for a set of integers of logarithmic density 1, in each macro-block of length $L(n)$ the minimum of the trajectory drops below n^β or else $T^{L(n)}(n) \leq n^{1-\gamma}$. The proof relies on (i) the exact bijection between classes modulo 2^L and parity prefixes of length L , (ii) uniform counting over consecutive intervals, (iii) a large deviation bound for odd-rich prefixes, (iv) a contraction inequality on a macro-block, and (v) a geometric summation over dyadic shells.

1 Introduction and main statement

We study the dynamics of the shortened Collatz transformation

$$T(n) = \begin{cases} n/2, & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ (3n + 1)/2, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

For $i \geq 0$, we denote T^i as the i -th iterate and $\varepsilon_i(n) \in \{0, 1\}$ as the parity of $T^i(n)$ (0 for even, 1 for odd). For $L \geq 1$, the *parity prefix* of length L is $P_L(n) = (\varepsilon_0(n), \dots, \varepsilon_{L-1}(n)) \in \{0, 1\}^L$, and the number of odd steps in this prefix is $K_L(n) = \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} \varepsilon_i(n)$.

Throughout the article, we adopt the convention $\log = \ln$ (natural logarithm) and \log_2 for the base-2 logarithm. Let us fix the constants

$$\tau \in (0, \tau_c), \quad \tau_c = \frac{1}{\log_2 3} - \frac{1}{2}, \quad \lambda \in \left(0, \frac{1}{\ln 2}\right), \quad \beta \in (0, 1),$$

and let

$$L(n) = \lfloor \lambda \ln n \rfloor, \quad \delta(\tau) = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{2} + \tau\right) \log_2 3 > 0.$$

Theorem 1 (Main Statement). *There exists $\gamma = \gamma(\tau, \lambda) > 0$ (for instance $\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \delta(\tau) \lambda \ln 2$) such that the set*

$$A = \left\{ n \geq 1 : \min_{0 \leq i < L(n)} T^i(n) \leq n^\beta \text{ or } T^{L(n)}(n) \leq n^{1-\gamma} \right\}$$

has logarithmic density 1, i.e., $\delta_{\log}(A) = 1$.

The proof is given in Sections 3–7. It is self-contained.

2 Notations, logarithmic density and an affine identity

Definition 2 (Logarithmic Density). For $E \subset \mathbb{N}$, we define

$$\delta_{\log}(E) = \lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\ln X} \sum_{\substack{n \leq X \\ n \in E}} \frac{1}{n},$$

when the limit exists. In particular, if $\sum_{n \in E} \frac{1}{n} < \infty$, then $\delta_{\log}(E) = 0$.

Lemma 3. *If $E \subset \mathbb{N}$ satisfies $\sum_{n \in E} \frac{1}{n} < \infty$, then $\delta_{\log}(E) = 0$.*

Proof. Let $S = \sum_{n \in E} \frac{1}{n} < \infty$. For any X ,

$$0 \leq \frac{1}{\ln X} \sum_{\substack{n \leq X \\ n \in E}} \frac{1}{n} \leq \frac{S}{\ln X} \xrightarrow{X \rightarrow \infty} 0.$$

□

We will use the following affine identity, obtained by unrolling the L steps of T .

Lemma 4 (Exact Affine Identity). *For any $n \geq 1$ and any $L \geq 0$, we have*

$$T^L(n) = \frac{3^{K_L(n)} n + C_L(n)}{2^L},$$

where $C_L(n) \in \mathbb{Z}$ is determined by the parity word $P_L(n)$ via the recurrence $C_0 = 0$ and, for $i = 0, \dots, L-1$,

$$C_{i+1} = \begin{cases} C_i, & \text{if } \varepsilon_i(n) = 0, \\ 3C_i + 2^i, & \text{if } \varepsilon_i(n) = 1. \end{cases}$$

Proof. By induction on L . The case $L = 0$ is trivial. Assume the formula holds for L . If $\varepsilon_L(n) = 0$, then $T^{L+1}(n) = \frac{1}{2} T^L(n) = \frac{3^{K_L n + C_L}}{2^{L+1}}$ and $K_{L+1} = K_L$, $C_{L+1} = C_L$. If $\varepsilon_L(n) = 1$, then $T^{L+1}(n) = \frac{3T^L(n)+1}{2} = \frac{3(3^{K_L n + C_L} + 2^L)}{2^{L+1}} = \frac{3^{K_{L+1} n + (3C_L + 2^L)}}{2^{L+1}}$ and $K_{L+1} = K_L + 1$, $C_{L+1} = 3C_L + 2^L$. □

3 Parity bijection and uniform counting

For $L \geq 1$, consider the map

$$P_L : \mathbb{Z}/2^L\mathbb{Z} \longrightarrow \{0, 1\}^L, \quad [n] \longmapsto (\varepsilon_0(n), \dots, \varepsilon_{L-1}(n)).$$

Lemma 5 (Bijection modulo 2^L). *For any $L \geq 1$, the map P_L is a bijection. In particular, for each word $\varepsilon = (\varepsilon_0, \dots, \varepsilon_{L-1}) \in \{0, 1\}^L$, the set $\{n \in \mathbb{Z} : P_L(n) = \varepsilon\}$ is exactly one congruence class modulo 2^L .*

Constructive proof by binary lifting. We reason by induction on $i = 0, 1, \dots, L$. For a fixed word $\varepsilon \in \{0, 1\}^L$, we uniquely construct a class $r_i \pmod{2^i}$ such that

$$n \equiv r_i \pmod{2^i} \iff P_i(n) = (\varepsilon_0, \dots, \varepsilon_{i-1}).$$

The case $i = 0$ is trivial. Assume $r_i \pmod{2^i}$ has been constructed. For any $n \equiv r_i \pmod{2^i}$, the prefix of length i is fixed, so by Lemma 4 there exist constants $A = 3^{K_i(\varepsilon)}$ and $B = C_i(\varepsilon)$ (depending only on the prefix $\varepsilon_0, \dots, \varepsilon_{i-1}$) such that

$$T^i(n) = \frac{An + B}{2^i}.$$

Consider the two possible liftings modulo 2^{i+1} : r_i and $r_i + 2^i$. We have

$$\frac{A(r_i + 2^i) + B}{2^i} \equiv \frac{Ar_i + B}{2^i} + A \pmod{2}.$$

Since $A = 3^{K_i(\varepsilon)}$ is odd, adding 2^i to n *flips* the parity of $T^i(n)$. It follows that exactly one of the two liftings produces $T^i(n)$ with parity ε_i . We define $r_{i+1} \pmod{2^{i+1}}$ as this unique lifting. Uniqueness and existence at each step imply that P_L is bijective. \square

Remark 6 (Explicit congruence formula). If $P_L(n) = \varepsilon$ and if $K = \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} \varepsilon_i$, $C = C_L(\varepsilon)$, then Lemma 4 gives $2^L \mid 3^K n + C$, i.e.

$$3^K n \equiv -C \pmod{2^L}.$$

Conversely, the proof above guarantees that an integer n satisfying this congruence has $P_L(n) = \varepsilon$. Since 3^K is invertible modulo 2^L , the class $n \pmod{2^L}$ is unique.

The previous lemma provides a uniform counting on consecutive intervals.

Corollary 7 (Uniform counting). *Let $L \geq 1$ and $S \subset \{0, 1\}^L$. For any interval of integers I of length N ,*

$$|\{n \in I : P_L(n) \in S\}| = \frac{N|S|}{2^L} \pm \min(2^L, |S|).$$

In particular, if $|S| \leq 2^L e^{-\alpha L}$, then

$$|\{n \in I : P_L(n) \in S\}| \leq N e^{-\alpha L} + 2^L e^{-\alpha L}.$$

Proof. Split I into $q = \lfloor N/2^L \rfloor$ consecutive blocks of length 2^L and a remainder R of length $< 2^L$. By Lemma 5, each full block contains exactly $|S|$ integers with a prefix in S . In R , there are at most $\min(|R|, |S|) \leq \min(2^L, |S|)$. \square

4 Large deviations for odd-rich prefixes

Lemma 8. *For $\tau > 0$ and $L \geq 1$, if*

$$B_L(\tau) = \{\varepsilon \in \{0, 1\}^L : \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} \varepsilon_i > (\frac{1}{2} + \tau)L\},$$

then $|B_L(\tau)|/2^L \leq e^{-2\tau^2 L}$.

Proof. Under the uniform measure on $\{0, 1\}^L$, $\sum \varepsilon_i \sim \text{Bin}(L, 1/2)$. The one-sided Hoeffding's inequality gives $\mathbb{P}(\sum \varepsilon_i \geq (\frac{1}{2} + \tau)L) \leq e^{-2\tau^2 L}$. \square

5 Control of the multiplicative factor due to odd steps

Lemma 9. *Let us fix $\beta \in (0, 1)$. If $\min_{0 \leq i < L} T^i(n) \geq n^\beta$, then*

$$\sum_{\substack{0 \leq i < L \\ \varepsilon_i(n)=1}} \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{3T^i(n)}\right) \leq \frac{K_L(n)}{3n^\beta} \leq \frac{L}{3n^\beta}.$$

Proof. We use $\ln(1+x) \leq x$ for $x \geq 0$ and $T^i(n) \geq n^\beta$ in each term of the sum. \square

6 Contraction inequality on a macro-block

Proposition 10. *Let $\tau \in (0, \tau_c)$, $\delta(\tau) = 1 - (\frac{1}{2} + \tau) \log_2 3 > 0$. There exists N_0 (depending on τ, λ, β) such that for any $n \geq N_0$, any $L \geq 1$ satisfying*

- (i) $K_L(n) \leq (\frac{1}{2} + \tau)L$,
- (ii) $\min_{0 \leq i < L} T^i(n) \geq n^\beta$,

we have

$$\ln T^L(n) \leq \ln n - \delta(\tau) L \ln 2 + \frac{L}{3n^\beta}.$$

In particular, if $L = \lfloor \lambda \ln n \rfloor$, then for n large enough

$$T^L(n) \leq n^{1-\gamma}, \quad \text{with } \gamma = \frac{1}{2} \delta(\tau) \lambda \ln 2 > 0.$$

Proof. By Lemma 4,

$$\mathsf{T}^L(n) = n \cdot 3^{K_L(n)} \cdot 2^{-L} \cdot \prod_{\substack{0 \leq i < L \\ \varepsilon_i(n)=1}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{3 \mathsf{T}^i(n)}\right).$$

By taking logarithms and using $K_L(n) \leq (\frac{1}{2} + \tau)L$ and Lemma 9,

$$\ln \mathsf{T}^L(n) \leq \ln n + K_L(n) \ln 3 - L \ln 2 + \frac{L}{3n^\beta} \leq \ln n - \delta(\tau) L \ln 2 + \frac{L}{3n^\beta}.$$

If $L = \lfloor \lambda \ln n \rfloor$, then $L/(3n^\beta) = o(\ln n)$, so for n large enough

$$\ln \mathsf{T}^L(n) \leq \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \delta(\tau) \lambda \ln 2\right) \ln n,$$

hence $\mathsf{T}^L(n) \leq n^{1-\gamma}$ with $\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \delta(\tau) \lambda \ln 2$. \square

7 Proof of Theorem 1

Let

$$A = \left\{n \geq 1 : \min_{0 \leq i < L(n)} \mathsf{T}^i(n) \leq n^\beta \text{ or } \mathsf{T}^{L(n)}(n) \leq n^{1-\gamma}\right\},$$

where $\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \delta(\tau) \lambda \ln 2 > 0$, and $E = \mathbb{N} \setminus A$ the set of exceptions. Then, for any $n \in E$,

$$\min_{0 \leq i < L(n)} \mathsf{T}^i(n) > n^\beta \quad \text{and} \quad K_{L(n)}(n) > \left(\frac{1}{2} + \tau\right)L(n). \quad (1)$$

We will show $\sum_{n \in E} \frac{1}{n} < \infty$, which will imply $\delta_{\log}(E) = 0$ via Lemma 3.

Consider the dyadic shells $I_k = [2^k, 2^{k+1} - 1]$ of length $|I_k| = 2^k$. Let us write $L_k = \lfloor \lambda k \ln 2 \rfloor$. Since $\lambda \ln 2 < 1$, we have, for $n \in I_k$,

$$L(n) = \lfloor \lambda \ln n \rfloor \in \{L_k, L_k + 1\}.$$

Let us introduce, for $L \in \{L_k, L_k + 1\}$, the set of "bad" prefixes

$$S_L = B_L(\tau) = \left\{\varepsilon \in \{0, 1\}^L : \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} \varepsilon_i > \left(\frac{1}{2} + \tau\right)L\right\}.$$

By (1), if $n \in E \cap I_k$ then $P_{L(n)}(n) \in S_{L(n)}$. Consequently,

$$|E \cap I_k| \leq |\{n \in I_k : P_{L_k}(n) \in S_{L_k}\}| + |\{n \in I_k : P_{L_k+1}(n) \in S_{L_k+1}\}|.$$

Let us apply Corollary 7 with Lemma 8: for $L \in \{L_k, L_k + 1\}$,

$$|\{n \in I_k : P_L(n) \in S_L\}| \leq 2^k e^{-2\tau^2 L} + 2^L e^{-2\tau^2 L}.$$

We deduce, for constants $C_1, C_2 > 0$ depending on (τ, λ) but independent of k ,

$$|E \cap I_k| \leq C_1 \cdot 2^k e^{-2\tau^2 L_k} + C_2 \cdot 2^L e^{-2\tau^2 L} \leq 2^k (e^{-c_1 k} + 2^{-c_2 k}),$$

where $c_1 = 2\tau^2 \lambda \ln 2 > 0$ and $c_2 = 1 - \lambda \ln 2 > 0$ (using $L_k \asymp \lambda k \ln 2$, $2^L \leq 2^{\lambda k \ln 2 + 1}$ and $e^{-2\tau^2 L} \leq 1$).

Finally, for $n \in I_k$ we have $2^{-k} \leq 1/n \leq 2^{-(k-1)}$, thus

$$\sum_{n \in E \cap I_k} \frac{1}{n} \leq |E \cap I_k| \cdot 2^{-(k-1)} \ll e^{-c_1 k} + 2^{-c_2 k}.$$

The sum over $k \geq 0$ is convergent (sum of geometric exponentials), hence $\sum_{n \in E} \frac{1}{n} < \infty$. By Lemma 3, $\delta_{\log}(E) = 0$ and therefore $\delta_{\log}(A) = 1$, which completes the proof of Theorem 1. \square

Final remarks

- Explicit choice of γ : any $\gamma \in (0, \delta(\tau)\lambda \ln 2)$ works; the proof takes $\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \delta(\tau)\lambda \ln 2$ to simplify the absorption of the term $L/(3n^\beta)$.
- The role of the constraint $\lambda < 1/\ln 2$ is twofold: (i) to ensure that $L(n)$ varies by at most 1 on each dyadic shell, and (ii) to guarantee the geometric decay of the boundary term $2^L/2^k$ with k .
- The parameter $\beta \in (0, 1)$ is only used to bound the product $\prod(1+1/(3T^i))$ by an $o(n^\varepsilon)$ on a block, via Lemma 9.